

Loading milk exosomes with urolithins boosts their delivery to the brain: Comparing the activity of encapsulated vs. free urolithins in SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells

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ABSTRACT

The gut microbial-derived metabolites of ellagitannins and ellagic acid, urolithins (Uros) are well-established anti-cancer metabolites according to preclinical studies. However, their efficacy is limited in systemic tissues, including the brain, by phase-II metabolism. Exosomes (EXOs), extracellular vesicles involved in cell signaling with the ability to cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB), could protect polyphenols from metabolism. Therefore, we loaded milk EXOs with Uro-A, Uro-B or IsoUro-A to evaluate their brain delivery and anticancer effects compared to non-encapsulated Uros. In Sprague-Dawley rats, perfused brain tissue analyses by UPLC-ESI-QTOF-MS showed higher Uro levels (~3–4-fold) at 5 min following intravenous administration of EXO-Uros compared to non-encapsulated Uros, except for Uro-B, using similar Uro concentrations (17–30 μM). Experiments on neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y cells revealed dose-dependent antiproliferative effects for all EXO-Uros (0.3–1.2 μM), but not with non-encapsulated Uros (10 μM). Flow cytometry analyses indicated that only EXO-Uros arrested the cell cycle and induced apoptosis. Finally, using fluorescent-labeled EXOs and selective inhibitors, the primary endocytic pathway was revealed to be clathrin-dependent. Overall, encapsulating Uros into EXOs is promising for enhancing brain delivery and anticancer activity.

1. Introduction

Currently, the use of exosomes (EXOs) is gaining research attention as promising nano-drug delivery vehicles, offering tremendous potential for several pharmaceutical and biomedical applications to the challenges faced by traditional therapeutic approaches (Gurunathan et al., 2019; Ha et al., 2016; Rajput et al., 2022). Mammalian and plant-derived EVs can serve as nano-drug delivery vehicles (del Pozo-Acebo et al., 2021; López de las Hazas et al., 2023). Among other advantages, their small size, low toxicity, longer half-life, biocompatibility, and efficient cellular exchange compared to synthetic drug carriers make EXOs an attractive option for delivering a wide range of therapeutic agents, particularly in cancer therapy (Gurunathan et al., 2019; Rajput et al., 2022). EXOs constitute the smallest subgroup of

cell-derived extracellular vesicles with an average particle size of 30–150 nm that are primarily responsible for cell-to-cell communications by transporting their cargo to the target cells, influencing their cellular environment (Kalluri & LeBleu, 2020; Mathivanan et al., 2010). Thus, the transport by EXOs of cell-specific cargos such as microRNA, mRNA, DNA, lipids or proteins to target cells plays crucial roles in multiple cellular functions involved in both physiological and pathological processes such as immune regulation, cell proliferation and differentiation, inflammation, neurodegeneration, and cancer (Gurung et al., 2021; Li et al., 2020; Soltész et al., 2021; Valadi et al., 2007). Furthermore, EXOs are present in almost all biological fluids, such as plasma, cerebrospinal fluid, saliva, urine, breast milk, etc., and have the ability to cross physical barriers, including the blood-brain barrier (BBB), so it is thought that they may play an important role in the brain

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(Gurunathan et al., 2019; Qing et al., 2018).

Bovine milk has been reported to contain a high amount of EXOs and possess several characteristics and advantages that make milk-derived EXOs an inexpensive alternative nanocarrier platform for encapsulating both hydrophilic and lipophilic agents, compared to plant food-derived EXOs, such as cross-species biocompatibility, no adverse immune and inflammatory responses, and further, the ability to cross the BBB (Munagala et al., 2016; Somiya et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2022). In this regard, milk-derived EXOs have been used in preclinical studies (cellular and animal models) to load unstable drugs, nucleic acids, and natural compounds, including phenolic compounds, reporting promising results in various aspects of health and tumor therapy by improving its delivery to systemic tissues (e.g. breast, brain, etc.) and (or) bioefficacy against cancer cells (Figueira et al., 2023; Munagala et al., 2017; Onizuka et al., 2023; Tian et al., 2023). To date, pioneered studies carried out with dietary phenolic compounds such as resveratrol or curcumin have confirmed that their encapsulation into EXOs overcome their low bioavailability and extensive phase-II metabolism, allowing them to reach systemic tissues as non-conjugated forms where they can exert higher anticancer activity compared with their corresponding conjugated phase-II forms (Aqil et al., 2017; Carobolante et al., 2020; González-Sarrías et al., 2022). Besides, to date, only a study has described that the encapsulation of curcumin in EXOs increased their delivery to the brain (Aqil et al., 2017).

Urolithins (Uros) are gut microbial metabolites derived from ellagic acid (occurring in foods such as pomegranate, some berries and nuts) and have been reported to possess potent anticancer, anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective effects in many preclinical studies (reviewed in (García-Villalba et al., 2022; García-Villalba et al., 2023). The potential antiproliferative/anticancer of Uros, primarily Uro-A, the main urolithin, but also for the other Uros (Uro-B and IsoUro-A) has been shown to block tumor growth, proliferation, and metastasis through multiple mechanisms such as induction of apoptosis, cell cycle arrest, promotion of senescence and autophagy, transcriptional regulation of oncogenes and signaling pathways, and inhibition of cell migration and invasion (Al-Harbi et al., 2021; Giménez-Bastida et al., 2020; González-Sarrías et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2018). Besides, *in silico* and preclinical studies have suggested that Uros could show favorable BBB permeability (Gasperotti et al., 2015; Kujawska et al., 2019, 2021; Yuan et al., 2016), which may greatly facilitate their neuroprotective effects, including their anticancer activities. However, relevant concerns limit the scope of these findings: i) once absorbed, phase-II enzymes extensively metabolize Uros, yielding phase-II conjugated metabolites (glucuronides and sulfates) that show much lower anticancer activity than their free forms (García-Villalba et al., 2022, 2023; González-Sarrías et al., 2014) and ii) after administration (oral or intravenous) of Uros in rodent models, glucuronidase and sulfatase-treated and (or) non-perfused brain samples were analyzed (Gasperotti et al., 2015; Kujawska et al., 2019, 2021). Thus, these approaches prevent determining whether the free bioactive Uros reach the brain and (or) are present in the brain parenchyma (or in circulation by not using perfused brains). Notably, a recent study has unequivocally reported the occurrence of non-conjugated Uro-A in perfused mice brains after intraperitoneal (*i.p.*) administration of Uro-A (Jiménez-Loygorri et al., 2024). Nevertheless, using EXOs as nanocarriers to encapsulate Uros for enhancing their delivery to the brain and their anticancer activity in human cancer cells has not been previously explored.

Thereby, for the first time, this study used the encapsulation of each of the major Uros (Uro-A, Uro-B and IsoUro-A) into milk-derived EXOs to improve their therapeutic potential by enhancing their bioavailability in the brain as well as their anticancer efficacy. To achieve these aims, we conducted an *in vivo* study to compare the kinetics and bio-distribution in perfused brains after administering intravenously free vs. encapsulated Uros into EXOs, at the same concentrations, in female Sprague-Dawley rats. Furthermore, we also aimed to compare the anticancer effects of free vs. encapsulated Uros in human neuroblastoma

SH-SY5Y cells using concentrations close to those achieved *in vivo*. Additionally, the cellular uptake mechanism of EXOs and the Uros metabolism were assayed on SH-SY5Y cells.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Reagents

Urolithins (Uro) metabolites Uro-A, Uro-B, and isourolithin A (Iso-Uro-A), and the conjugates Uro-A 3-glucuronide (Uro-A-glur), Uro-B glucuronide (Uro-B-glur), IsoUro-A 3-glucuronide (IsoUro-A-glur) and Uro-A sulfate (Uro-A-sulf) conjugates, were obtained from Villapharma Research S.L. (Parque Tecnológico de Fuente Alamo, Murcia, Spain). Purity was higher than 95% for all compounds. Trypan blue, bovine serum albumin (BSA), MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide), RNase, Annexin V/PI detection kit, and the inhibitors of cellular uptake phenylarsine oxide (Phe), monensin (Mon), chlorpromazine (Chlor) and cytochalasin D (Cyt) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). HPLC-grade acetonitrile (ACN), formic acid, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and methanol (MeOH) were obtained from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Phosphate buffer saline (PBS) was obtained from Fisher Scientific (Madrid, Spain). Ultrapure Millipore water was used throughout the study.

2.2. Isolation, purification, and characterization of milk-derived exosomes (EXOs)

Exosomes (EXOs) were isolated from raw bovine milk as previously described (López de las Hazas et al., 2022). Briefly, raw milk was centrifuged through a series of centrifugations, including at 15,000×g for 30 min for cell and fat globule removal and at 35,000×g for 60 min at 4 °C for other contaminants removal. The supernatant was ultracentrifuged at 100,000×g for 105 min using an OPTIMA XPN-100 Ultracentrifuge (Beckman Coulter Eurocenter S.A., Nyon, Switzerland) with a 50.2 Ti rotor. The fluffy layer was filtered through a 0.22 µm filter and purified by size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a Sepharose column 2B® (Sigma-Aldrich). EXOs were analyzed by protein concentration and characterized by Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis (NTA), electron microscopy and Western Blotting (WB).

EXOs were characterized in terms of size, concentration, and zeta potential (ZP) by NTA using the ZetaView TWIN® (Particle Metrix, Inning am Ammersee, Germany). Size and concentration were determined at room temperature by a 488 nm laser and fluorescence by a 640 nm laser. EV samples were appropriately diluted (1:100,000) in warm filtered PBS (0.22 µm filter) for size and concentration and ultrapure water for ZP. Analyses were performed using the NanoSight NTA 3.1. Program (Malvern instrument, UK). NTA analysis was performed on fresh samples. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) with negative staining was performed using a copper grid (200 mesh) and stained with 1% uranyl acetate. Samples were examined (100 kV) on a JEOL JEM 1010 (Spanish National Centre for Electron Microscopy, ICTS, Madrid, Spain). WB was assessed as previously described (González-Sarrías et al., 2022) using *anti*-Hsp 90 (610418, BD Biosciences, Madrid, Spain), *anti*-CD63 (bs-1523R, Bioss, Woburn, MA, USA), *anti*-TSG101 (A303-506A, Bethyl, Montgomery, TX, USA), *anti*-calnexin (A303-694A, Bethyl), and *anti*-β-casein (ab112595, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) as primary antibodies. Antirabbit or anti-mouse conjugated secondary antibodies were used with either Alexa Fluor™ 680 or IRDye® 800. Images were obtained using an Odyssey® infrared imaging system (LI-COR, Lincoln, NE, USA). Image Studio Lite 5.2.5 software was employed for image processing.

2.3. Encapsulation, characterization and analysis of uros into milk-derived EXOs

Precipitated and filtered EXOs (0.22 µm filter) were subjected to

Uros loading. Loading was performed as previously described (González-Sarrías et al., 2022). Briefly, Uros were dissolved in ethanol (EtOH) and exposed to EXOs by passive incubation at room temperature in the dark, rocking at 40 rpm for 1h. Loaded EXOs were further purified by SEC to eliminate non-loaded Uros and other protein contaminants. Purified EXO fractions from SEC were combined for further characterization, analysis and concentration. Purified loaded EXOs were concentrated by ultracentrifugation at $100,000\times g$ for 105 min. Precipitated EXOs were resuspended in PBS and aseptically filtered using a $0.22\ \mu\text{m}$ filter and kept in sterile conditions for further analysis. Aliquots were kept for characterization analysis. Finally, as previously described, $50\ \mu\text{L}$ of each EXO-Uros were extracted and analyzed by UPLC-ESI-QTOF-MS to quantify the concentration of each Uro loaded in EXOs (González-Sarrías et al., 2022).

2.4. Kinetic disposition of uros in the rat-perfused brain tissue

The experimental protocol followed a protocol approved by the animal ethics committee (University of Murcia, Spain) and the local government (reference 837/2022). All experiments achieved followed the Directive of the European Council 63/2010/UE and the Spanish government (RD 53/2013). Female Sprague-Dawley rats ($n = 57$) with weights ranging from 200 to 220 g were provided by the Experimental Animal Service of the University of Murcia. Animals were randomly assigned to seven groups ($n = 9$ rats per group; 4–5 rats per cage) in a temperature-controlled environment ($22 \pm 2\ ^\circ\text{C}$) with $55\% \pm 10\%$ relative humidity and controlled lighting (12-h light/dark cycle). All rats were fed with rat standard chow ad libitum until the start of the experiments (Panlab, Barcelona, Spain).

Fig. 1 shows the animal study design. Groups 1–3, EXO-Uro-A ($300\ \mu\text{L}$, equivalent to $0.59\ \text{mg}$ EXO protein, and containing $30\ \mu\text{M}$ Uro-A), EXO-Uro-B ($300\ \mu\text{L}$, equivalent to $0.53\ \text{mg}$ EXO protein, containing $17\ \mu\text{M}$ Uro-B) or EXO-IsoUro-A ($300\ \mu\text{L}$, equivalent to $0.56\ \text{mg}$ EXO protein, containing $24\ \mu\text{M}$ IsoUro-A) were administered intravenously (*i. v.*) to isoflurane-sedated rats. In parallel, the same approach was followed for administering each free (non-encapsulated) Uro (groups 4–6; Uro-A ($30\ \mu\text{M}$), Uro-B ($17\ \mu\text{M}$) or IsoUro-A ($24\ \mu\text{M}$) dissolved in PBS: EtOH (95:5). A group control ($n = 1$ each time-point) (group 7; without

i. v. administration) was also conducted. According to previous studies (González-Sarrías et al., 2022), after 3, 5, and 15 min of administration ($n = 3$ each time-point), sedated rats were sacrificed using a CO_2 chamber. After slaughter, blood samples were collected in EDTA-treated tubes by cardiac puncture and processed as described elsewhere (Ávila-Gálvez et al., 2019). Next, animals were perfused with ice-cold phosphate-buffered saline, and the blood-free brain was dissected out immediately and stored at $-80\ ^\circ\text{C}$ until analysis, as detailed previously (Abd El Mohsen et al., 2002). Uros and derived metabolites in exosomes, blood, and perfused brain tissue were analyzed using UPLC-ESI-QTOF-MS as previously described (Ávila-Gálvez et al., 2019).

2.5. Cell culture

As a cellular model, we used the SH-SY5Y human neuroblastoma cell line from the European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures (ECACC) (Salisbury, UK). According to the ECACC recommendations, the culture medium selected was Ham's F12:EMEM (EBSS) (1:1) enriched with FBS (15% v/v) and supplemented with 2 mM glutamine + 1% non-essential amino acids. Cells were incubated at $37\ ^\circ\text{C}$ in a humidified atmosphere of 95% air/5% CO_2 .

2.6. Cell treatments and viability

Cells were exposed to Uro-A, Uro-B or IsoUro-A-loaded EXO (EXO-Uro-A, EXO-Uro-B, and EXO-IsoUro-A, respectively) at a range of concentrations ($0.3\text{--}1.2\ \mu\text{M}$) closely found in the rat perfused brain tissue as detailed in *in vivo* kinetics. These concentrations were selected based on the maximum milk-derived EXO percentage in the cell culture without affecting the osmolarity and pH of the cell inside the incubator using a vapor pressure osmometer 5520 (VAPRO Wescor, Utah, USA) and a pH indicator paper (Neutralit, pH 5.5–9.0, Merck, Madrid, Spain). In parallel, $10\ \mu\text{M}$ of each corresponding free Uros (non-encapsulated in EXOs) and non-loaded EXOs (EXO-CT) were also assayed. Untreated cells (CT, control) were also run in parallel and subjected to the same changes in a medium with 5% PBS.

Cells (5×10^3 cells/well) were seeded in 96-well plates and were incubated for one day to allow for attachment and acclimatization. SH-

Fig. 1. Experimental design of the kinetic study.

SY5Y cells were treated with each treatment for 72 h. As described elsewhere, cell viability was measured using the MTT assay to assess the dose-dependent antiproliferative effects of each treatment (González-Sarrías, Núñez-Sánchez, Tomás-Barberán, & Espín, 2017). The cytotoxic effect was calculated as the percentage of cell proliferation values compared to the control cells (5% PBS; 100%). Data are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Assays were repeated at least three times ($n = 3$). The treatments were tested in 6–8 different wells in each assay.

2.7. Cell cycle analysis and assessment of apoptosis by flow cytometry

The mechanism of action involved in the antiproliferative effect exerted by EXO-Uros was evaluated by flow cytometry (FACStation running Cell Quest software, Becton Dickinson, New Jersey, USA) measuring the cell cycle distribution and apoptosis induction using the annexin V/PI detection kit by identifying both early and late apoptosis (Molecular Probes, ThermoFisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain) (González-Sarrías et al., 2015). Cells were treated with each of the three free Uros (Uro-A, Uro-B and IsoUro-A) at 10 μ M and the corresponding loaded EXOs (EXO-Uro-A, EXO-Uro-B, and EXO-IsoUro-A) at 1 μ M for 3 days of treatment. In parallel, non-loaded EXOs (EXO-CT) and untreated cells (CT, control) were also evaluated. Data are shown as the mean \pm SD of 3 independent experiments (2 wells per treatment) for each time point.

2.8. Labeled milk-derived EXO uptake by SH-SY5Y cells

EXOs were fluorescently labeled using commercial cyanine (SCy) 7.5 NHS ester (Lumiprobe, Hannover, Germany) as previously described (González et al., 2021). Briefly, a solution of 75 μ g of EXOs in 100 μ L PBS was mixed with 10 μ L SCy 7.5 (17 mM) at pH 8.5 (with NaHCO₃ 0.1 M) and rocking overnight at 4 °C and protected from light. The product was purified by ultracentrifugation at 100,000 \times g for 105 min. Next, covalently labeled EXOs were resuspended in sterile PBS, filtered through a 0.22 μ m sterile filter and kept sterile for further experiments.

SH-SY5Y cells were seeded on 24-well plates with coverslips (80,000 cells/well) and grown for 48 h. The cellular uptake of labeled milk-derived non-loaded EXOs was evaluated in the presence and absence of four specific inhibitors involved in endocytic pathways (phenylarsine oxide as general endocytosis inhibitor and chlorpromazine, involved in clathrin-mediated endocytosis), microtubule assembly (cytochalasin D), and lysosome binding (monensin). This evaluation was conducted for 4 h at non-cytotoxic doses, as previously reported (González-Sarrías et al., 2022). When inhibitors were used, cells were pre-incubated with the inhibitors for 15 min before adding labeled EXOs. After the treatments, the cells were fixed with paraformaldehyde 4%, washed 3 times with PBS, and maintained at 4 °C for no longer than 2 weeks. Nuclei were counterstained using Invitrogen™ ProLong Gold Antifade Mountant with DAPI. Cell images were acquired using a confocal microscope, Leica STELLARIS 8 (Wetzlar, Germany), using 63 \times glycerol immersion objectives. Four fields per condition were acquired and evaluated for semi-quantitative analysis. Immunofluorescence images obtained by confocal microscopy were examined using Icy (Institute Pasteur and France BioImaging, Paris, France) and ImageJ (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA) software. Total cell fluorescence intensity was quantified using 10 cells per field, and the polygon tool was used from the Icy software. Data are shown as the mean \pm SD of 3 independent experiments (2 wells per treatment).

2.9. Assessment of stability and phase-II metabolism of free uros and EXO-encapsulated uros in SH-SY5Y cells

The stability and cell metabolism (phase-II conjugation) of each Uro by SH-SY5Y cells were determined at 0 and 72 h. Cell media were collected at each time point, processed, and analyzed by UPLC-ESI-

QTOF-MS as described elsewhere (Ávila-Gálvez et al., 2018).

2.10. Statistical analysis

Data were expressed as the average \pm standard deviation (SD). A two-tailed unpaired Student's *t*-test was used for statistical analysis of the data using SPSS Software, version 27.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Graphs were performed using GraphPad Prism 9.1.1 software (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). A value of $P < 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of uros encapsulated in milk exosomes

We first isolated EXOs from raw bovine milk by ultracentrifugation (UC) and loaded with Uros by passive incubation. Loaded EXOs were further purified by size exclusion chromatography (SEC), and purified exosome fractions (F8 to F9) from SEC (Fig. 2A) were combined for characterization by Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) (Fig. 2B). Protein (\sim 1.86 mg/mL) and particle concentration (\sim 5 \times 10¹² particles/mL) were similar in all EXOs (Fig. 2C). Z-potential was negative (\sim 22.65 mV) for all EXOs, and size slightly increased after loading (\sim 7 nm). Proteins were analyzed by Western blot analysis to verify that milk-derived EXOs maintain some of their protein characteristics after loading (Fig. 2D). Milk-derived EXOs contained the EXO marker proteins CD63, TSG101, HSP90, Alix and CD9, whereas the non-EXO protein calnexin was absent. Electron microscopy analysis showed similar sizes and shapes of EXOs, whether loaded or not (Fig. 2E). Overall, the data show that Uros loading, through passive diffusion, did not change EXOs' main characteristics and were used for downstream experiments.

Compared to previous studies where (poly)phenols were also loaded by passive diffusion (González-Sarrías et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2010; Tréton et al., 2023), urolithins reached higher concentrations (30 μ M for Uro-A, 17 μ M for Uro-B or 24 μ M for IsoUro-A) within milk-derived EXOs.

3.2. In vivo enhancement of urolithins bioavailability via milk-exosome encapsulation

Three Uros (Uro-A, Uro-B and IsoUro-A), free or encapsulated in milk-derived EXOs, were administered to female SD rats. Fig. 3 illustrates the pharmacokinetic profiles (in plasma and brain) of the three different Uros after *i. v.* injection at 3, 5, and 15 min.

Fig. 3A shows the plasma and perfused-brain distribution of EXO-Uro-A and free Uro-A administration. Both in plasma and brain, Uro-A peaked at 5 min (Tmax) regardless of the administration form (encapsulated or free). Uro-A levels at Tmax (Cmax) were 3-fold (brain) and 9-fold (plasma) higher for EXO-Uros compared to free Uros.

Regarding Uro-B, the scenario was different. While EXO-Uro-B peaked in plasma at 5 min, its non-encapsulated administration peaked at 3 min. In the case of the brain, the Tmax for Uro-B was 3 min regardless of the administration form. Additionally, although no quantitative differences were observed at any evaluated time point, encapsulating Uro-B in EXOs seemed to sustain its concentration over time (5 and 15 min), reaching values around 9 pmol/g tissue of free Uro-B when encapsulated compared to values from 2- to 3-fold lower for the non-encapsulated form (Fig. 3B). However, it should not be ruled out that Uro-B, due to its smaller size, might have a greater ability to cross the BBB and the improvement when encapsulated in EXOs may not be very significant.

Finally, after EXO-IsoUro-A administration, plasma IsoUro-A concentrations were up to 2-fold higher than those detected after administering the non-encapsulated IsoUro-A (Fig. 3C). The Tmax exhibited different patterns, as the administration of non-encapsulated IsoUro-A peaked at 3 min while the EXO-IsoUro-A peaked at 15 min. A similar

Fig. 2. Milk-derived exosomes characterization by different methods. (A) Protein concentration (mg/mL) of 40 SEC fractions measured by BCA. The image shown is representative of multiple experiments with similar results. (B) Size and distribution profiles of EXOs (EXO-CT, EXO-Uro-A, EXO-Uro-B, EXO-IsoUro-A) measured by NTA. (C) Main characteristics of each EXOs fractions: particle concentration (particles/mL), particles size (nm), z-potential (mV) and total protein concentration (mg/mL). (D) Western blot analysis of characteristic proteins of EXOs (CD63, TSG101, CD9, Hsp-90, and Alix) from selected fractions of SEC. Fractions containing EXOs (F7, F8, F9) and some representative upstream and downstream fractions were analyzed. Calnexin was used as a control to discard cell contamination. (E) Images of EXO fractions obtained by transmission electron microscopy (scale bar: 100 nm). NTA, nanoparticle tracking analysis; SEC, size exclusion chromatography.

pattern was observed in the brain, with the highest concentration achieved at 3 min when it was non-encapsulated, compared to the 5 min observed for the EXO-IsoUro-A administration, showing around 6-fold higher concentration.

The enhanced delivery in the brain of Uros when encapsulated in

EXOs agrees with a few studies that reported higher penetration of resveratrol or curcumin through the BBB, thus increasing their concentration in the brain when encapsulated in EXOs derived from primary microglia treated with resveratrol or RAW 264.7 cells-derived EXOs, respectively (Fan et al., 2020; Jia et al., 2018). In addition to this, to the

Fig. 3. Plasma and brain kinetics of Uro-A (A), Uro-B (B) and IsoUro-A (C). EXO-Uros and free Uros were administered by intravenous injection (30, 17 and 24 µM for Uro-A, Uro-B and IsoUro-A, respectively) in female Sprague-Dawley rats, either encapsulated into milk-derived exosomes (EXOs) or non-encapsulated at 3, 5, and 15 min. Plasma and perfused brain samples were analyzed by UPLC-QTOF-MS. Data represent the average ± SD of three animals at each time point.

best of our knowledge, only two previous studies have reported that the encapsulation into milk-derived EXOS enhances the delivery of curcumin and resveratrol in systemic tissues such as liver, lung, breast and brain (Aqil et al., 2017; González-Sarrías et al., 2022). In this line, the oral administration of EXO-curcumin vs. free curcumin at equivalent doses showed higher levels (up to 6-fold) of curcumin in the brain, suggesting that EXOs could facilitate higher bioaccumulation of curcumin in the brain (Aqil et al., 2017). However, it should be noted that these authors analyzed non-perfused brains. Therefore, the occurrence of curcumin in the brain parenchyma was not unequivocally demonstrated, and thus, these concentrations could be different. Our results support the notion that encapsulating phenolics into EXOs could facilitate brain delivery by achieving higher concentrations, which could be relevant for exerting brain health effects targeting brain diseases. This fact is in line with growing innovative strategies encapsulating drugs into EXOs to overcome biological and chemical barriers as well as protect molecules from efflux transporters (Azarmi et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2018). Indeed, as a drug delivery system, several routes of

administration have been tested for bioactive compounds, including inhalable system (Qiu et al., 2024), local transdermal administration (Wen et al., 2024), systemic (González-Sarrías et al., 2022) or oral delivery (Aqil et al., 2017; Munagala et al., 2016), among others. In agreement with our results, and as first described for brain delivery, the EXOs-loaded compounds exerted higher delivery capacity in most cases than the non-encapsulated compounds (Aqil et al., 2017; González-Sarrías et al., 2022) suggesting that exosomes have real potential applications in drug delivery systems.

On the other hand, regarding the formation of phase-II metabolites in plasma, both glucuronide and sulfate forms were detected for each of the Uros. However, no major differences were observed (Fig. 3A–C). Thus, unlike those described in previous studies where administering curcumin or resveratrol alone or encapsulated in cell lines-derived EXOs to rodent models *i. p.*, the concentration in plasma resulted up to 5-fold higher for curcumin or 2-fold for resveratrol when encapsulated (Fan et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2010) in our study no differences were observed in the stability or phase II metabolism after *i. v.* administration.

Interestingly, no glucuronides were detected in the brain when Uros were administered either in EXOs or free, in agreement with Jiménez-Loygorry et al. (Jiménez-Loygorry et al., 2024). Only Uro-A-sulf was detected in the brain when Uro-A was administered free. On the other hand, concentrations of Uro-B-sulf were detected at all three different time points, either after its administration in EXOs or as free forms.

3.3. Enhanced antiproliferative and anticancer effects of EXO-Uros vs. free forms

The antiproliferative activity of each Exo-Uro was determined in subconfluent SH-SY5Y cells, which were incubated with non-cytotoxic doses (5% in culture medium) after calculating the maximum percentage of milk-derived EXO in the cell culture without affecting the osmolarity and pH of the cellular medium (pH 7 and osmolality values of 285–305 mmol/kg, respectively). First, the cell proliferation after the non-encapsulated EXOs (EXO-CT) treatment (5% dose) was above 90% of cell proliferation, similar to untreated cells (control, CT) at 72 h. The data showed that, unlike free Uros (10 μM), which did not exert any antiproliferative effect, a dose-dependent statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) antiproliferative efficacy of the three EXO-Uros was observed even at lower concentrations (0.36–1.2 μM) compared to EXO-CT (Fig. 4) after 72 h of treatment. The lack of anti-proliferative effect on SH-SY5Y cells of non-encapsulated Uros at doses up to 15 μM after 24-h exposure has been previously reported, while higher concentrations with doubtful physiological relevance of Uro-B and Uro-A (20, 50 and 100 μM) decreased the viability of these cells (Abbasinezhad-Moud et al., 2023; An et al., 2023; González-Sarrías, Núñez-Sánchez, Tomás-Barberán, & Espín, 2017). The present study corroborates that the encapsulation of phenolics or derived metabolites, in this case, Uros, increases anticancer activity in comparison with their non-encapsulated forms, in agreement with previous studies carried out with resveratrol and curcumin (Aqil et al., 2017; Carobolante et al., 2020; González-Sarrías et al., 2022).

No statistically significant differences in the anti-proliferative effect were observed among the three EXO-Uros. However, a slight trend indicated a higher effect of EXO-Uro-A than others, showing higher cell viability inhibition at the highest dose tested (1.06 μM vs. 0.99 and 1.20 μM for EXO-Uro-B and EXO-IsoUro-A, respectively). Besides, the EXO-

Fig. 4. Comparison of the cell proliferation inhibition of SH-SY5Y cells after treatment with free Uros (Uro-A, Uro-B and IsoUro-A) (10 μM) and their corresponding EXO-Uros ranging concentrations from 0.3 to 1.2 μM after 72 h. EXO-CT, non-loaded milk-derived EXOs (5%). ^a $P < 0.05$ vs. untreated cells, CT, ^b $P < 0.01$ vs. EXO-CT).

IsoUroA treatment was not statistically significant at the lowest dose tested (0.3 μM) compared to EXO-CT. In contrast, EXO-UroA still showed antiproliferative activity at 0.36 μM ($P < 0.05$) (Fig. 4).

The impact of encapsulation in EXOs on the antiproliferative/anticancer capacity of Uros was examined by assessing the effect on cell cycle distribution and apoptosis induction at concentrations of 10 and 1 μM for free Uros and EXO-Uros, respectively. Regarding the cell cycle distribution, the analysis showed a statistically significant increase of the S phase with the concomitant decrease of the G_0/G_1 phase after treatment with all Uros-loaded EXO, but not with their corresponding free forms despite the highest dose tested compared with CT and EXO-CT cells ($P < 0.05$) (Fig. 5). Besides, although no differences were observed between EXO-Uros treatments, a modest increase (but statistically significant; $P < 0.05$) at G_2/M after EXO-Uro-A treatment was observed compared with CT cells (Fig. 5).

Although cell cycle arrest depends on both the compound tested and the cell line, the effect of Uros on these cells, as well as the stronger effect of Uro-A, shares similarities with observations in other cancer cell lines such as colon (González-Sarrías et al., 2009, 2017a), González-Sarrías, Núñez-Sánchez, Tomás-Barberán, & Espín, 2017) ladder (Liberal et al., 2017) and brain cancer cells (Liu et al., 2022). Furthermore, the effect on the cell cycle seems to be more dependent on the type of compound and (or) cell line than the form of administration. This was evidenced by a study carried out with EXO-resveratrol and EXO-curcumin in breast cancer MCF-7 cells, where an increase in the G_0/G_1 phase and a decrease in the S phase was observed (González-Sarrías et al., 2022).

On the other hand, the apoptosis analysis indicated that the three EXO-Uros treatments exerted a statistically significant increase (~5-fold) in the number of early apoptotic cells compared with EXO-CT and CT cells. In contrast, free Uros were ineffective, even at higher concentrations than those tested for EXO-Uros (Fig. 6). Like cell cycle arrest, the induction of apoptosis as an anticancer mechanism exerted by Uros has been well-documented in many previous studies conducted in different cancer cell lines (Al-Harbi et al., 2021; García-Villalba et al., 2022). Besides, this finding agrees with that observed for EXO-resveratrol and EXO-curcumin in breast cancer MCF-7 that reported apoptosis induction via the mitochondrial pathway in a p53-independent mechanism (González-Sarrías et al., 2022). Therefore, these findings corroborate that the encapsulation of phenolics or derived metabolites into EXOs increases apoptosis, cell cycle arrest and decreases proliferation.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the cell cycle distribution after treatment with free Uros (10 μM) vs. EXO-Uros (1 μM) in SH-SY5Y cells after 72 h. EXO-CT, non-loaded milk-derived EXOs (5%). ^a $P < 0.05$ vs. untreated cells, CT, ^b $P < 0.01$ vs. EXO-CT).

Fig. 6. Comparison of the apoptosis induction exerted by free Uros (10 μ M) vs. EXO-Uros (1 μ M) in SH-SY5Y cells after 72 h. EXO-CT, non-loaded milk-derived EXOs (5%). ^a $P < 0.05$ vs. untreated cells, CT, ^b $P < 0.01$ vs. EXO-CT.

However, the opposite effects that could enhance its (neuro)protective effects against tumor, inflammatory or oxidative damage should also be considered. In this line, a study conducted in rotenone-induced SH-SY5Y cells reported the neuroprotective effect of milk-derived EXO-epicatechin gallate (ECG) compared to free ECG (Luo et al., 2021).

Finally, it is noteworthy that encapsulation into EXOS enhanced the anticancer effects of Uros on SH-SY5Y cells using plausible physiological concentrations (nanomolar) detected in the perfused brain. However, while SH-SY5Y cells, which exhibit characteristics of immature neuronal cells, are commonly used in neuroscience and cancer research due to their derivation from human neuroblastoma, which typically occurs in the sympathetic nervous system, they may not fully recapitulate the complex brain tumor microenvironment found *in vivo*. Therefore, future studies should evaluate this enhanced anticancer effect of encapsulated Uros into EXOs against brain cancer cell models such as glioblastoma. Thus, both Uro-A and Uro-B have been reported to inhibit cell proliferation, migration and invasion of different glioblastoma cell models, inducing cell cycle arrest and apoptosis, among other mechanisms, at concentrations above 5 μ M, which could hardly be reached in the brain (Eidizade et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2022; Shen et al., 2023).

3.4. Cellular metabolism of free uros and EXO-uros by SH-SY5Y cells

We next investigated the metabolism of each Uro, both in its free form (10 μ M) and encapsulated in EXOs (1 μ M), in SH-SY5Y cells after cell media analysis by UPLC-ESI-QTOF-MS at 0 and 72 h. Analyses showed that all Uros were stable in the cell media during the assay (up to 72 h). In addition, a low cell metabolism (sulfation) of Uros, less than 5%, was observed after 72 h of incubation of free forms (Fig. S1). A similar pattern of cell metabolism was observed when EXO-Uros were incubated, showing a small amount of sulfate conjugates, while no glucuronide conjugates were detected (Fig. S2).

Previous studies have described the phase-II conjugation of Uros into glucuronide and sulfate metabolites in cell models, especially in colon cancer cells (González-Sarrías et al., 2014, 2017a) and at a lower rate in systemic cancer cell models such as breast (Ávila-Gálvez et al., 2018), limiting their anticancer effect. However, to the best of our knowledge, the metabolism of Uros by SH-SY5Y cells has not been reported so far. Besides, only one study has reported that phenolics such as quercetin and luteolin were converted to their *O*-methylated metabolites by these cells but not other conjugated metabolites, even though the content of these phenolics decreased after 24 h of culture, suggesting an instability of the compounds (Bandaruk et al., 2014), unlike to the stability shown

in our study by Uros. Overall, these findings suggest that the differences in the anticancer effect between EXO-Uros and free Uros were not due to differences in their metabolism by the cells.

3.5. Cellular uptake mechanisms of milk-derived exosomes in SH-SY5Y cells

In order to explore the cellular uptake mechanism of milk-derived EXOs, four specific endocytosis inhibitors were used to evaluate possible endocytic pathways involved in the internalization of EXOs by SH-SY5Y cells. Phenylarsine oxide (Phe) is a clathrin-coated endocytic vesicles inhibitor, cytochalasin D (Cyt) is a known inhibitor of actin polymerization and phagocytosis, monensin (Mon) affects the endocytic pathway associated with early endosomes, and chlorpromazine (Chlor) inhibits clathrin-dependent endocytosis inducing a redistribution of clathrin-coated pit component to endosomes (Doherty & McMahon, 2009; Gao et al., 2013; Mayor & Pagano, 2007).

Finally, we covalently labeled EXOs with SCy 7.5 NHS to determine the cellular localization of uptake EXOs. Labeled EXOs were characterized by NTA to confirm effective labeling. Fig. 7A shows confocal images of representative SH-SY5Y cells treated with labeled EXO-CT in the presence of Phe, Cyt, Mon, and Chlor, respectively. Red fluorescence corresponds to EXOs internalized within the cells. As shown in Fig. 7B, treatment with all of the inhibitors significantly decreased ($P < 0.05$) EXO uptake. None of the applied inhibitors completely blocked the uptake of labeled vesicles. However, Phe and Chlor showed the most pronounced inhibitory impact, indicating that the clathrin-dependent pathway might serve as the primary intracellular route for EXO uptake. This agrees with other studies using milk-derived EXOs containing curcumin or resveratrol that reported a cellular uptake in breast, cancer and lung cancer cells primarily via clathrin-mediated endocytosis (Aqil et al., 2017; González-Sarrías et al., 2022; Wolf et al., 2015). Many uptake pathways have been identified, varying in the cargoes they transport and the protein machinery facilitating the endocytic process (Mayor & Pagano, 2007). These pathways involved clathrin-mediated endocytosis, lipid-raft mediated, caveolin-mediated endocytosis, phagocytosis or micropinocytosis, which are not always mutually exclusive and can co-exist to internalize the same set of exosomes (Gurung et al., 2021). In the present study, although the uptake of EXO by neuroblastoma cells appears to occur through several pathways, the clathrin-mediated pathway seems to be the most predominant, consistent with a previous study (González-Sarrías et al., 2022). Finally, the cellular localization (cytoplasm or nucleus) of EXOs within the cells was also evaluated. From the semi-quantitative analysis, we observed that EXOs were primarily found in the cytoplasm. However, a small percentage (about 2%) of EXOs was also detected in the nucleus (yellow circles) (Fig. 7C).

4. Conclusion

The results showed for the first time that Uros could be successfully encapsulated into milk-derived EXOs to enhance their brain delivery and anticancer activity on human neuroblastoma cells, using plausible *in vivo* concentrations. Up to now, although milk-derived exosomes (EXOs) have gained popularity in recent years as drug carriers to increase the transport of bioactives, their ability to cross the BBB had only been explored in one study conducted with curcumin (Aqil et al., 2017). Herein, remarkably, the administration of free (non-encapsulated) Uros, even at a 10-fold higher concentration, failed to exert antiproliferative activity, cell cycle arrest and apoptotic induction, observed for EXO-Uros, favored by cellular internalization of EXOs via clathrin-dependent endocytosis. Further research exploring the efficacy of Uros encapsulated in EXOs *in vivo* is warranted to confirm their therapeutic potential against brain cancer and other systemic cancers.

Fig. 7. Uptake of milk-derived exosomes in SH-SY5Y cells. SH-SY5Y cells were treated with sulfo-cyanine5-labeled exosomes (2.5%) for 4 h. (A) Confocal immunofluorescence detection of EXO-CT (red) in the presence or absence of different inhibitors involved in cellular uptake mechanisms: phenylarsine oxide (Phe), cytochalasin D (Cyt), monensin (Mon), and chlorpromazine (Chlor). DAPI was used as counterstaining for the nucleus. (B) Semi-quantitative analysis revealed a decrease in EXO intensity at 4 h of incubation in the presence of the different inhibitors. One-way ANOVA Tukey's multiple comparisons was used to evaluate the significant differences between the different inhibitors treatments. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences ($P < 0.05$ ($n = 3$)). (C) Relative subcellular distribution of EXOs from the semi-quantitative analysis using the ratio between cytoplasm and nucleus fluorescence. Confocal images (captured at $\times 100$ magnification) showing EXO localization within the nucleus (indicated by yellow circles). Scale bar: 10 μm . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Notes

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

María Ángeles Ávila-Gálvez: Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Salvador Romero-Reyes:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **María del Carmen López de las Hazas:** Writing – review &

editing, Methodology. **Andrea del Saz-Lara:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Alberto Dávalos:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Juan Carlos Espín:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Antonio González-Sarriás:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

ABBREVIATIONS

ACN	Acetonitrile;
BBB	blood-brain barrier
BSA	bovine serum albumin
DMSO	dimethyl sulfoxide
Chlor	chlorpromazine
CT	control
Cyt	cytochalasin D
ECACC	European collection of authenticated cell cultures
ECG	epicatechin gallate
EMEM	Eagle's minimal essential medium
ESI	electrospray ionization
EtOH	ethanol
EXO	exosome
EXO-Uros	Uros encapsulated in exosomes
FBS	Fetal bovine serum
glur	glucuronide
HPLC	high-performance liquid chromatography
<i>i.p.</i>	intraperitoneal
<i>i.v.</i>	intravenous
IsoUro	isourolithin
MeOH	methanol
Mon	monensin
MS	mass spectrometry
MTT	(3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide)
NTA	nanoparticle tracking analysis
PBS	phosphate buffer saline
Phe	phenylarsine oxide
QTOF	quadrupole-time-of-flight
SEC	size-exclusion chromatography
SD	standard deviation
sulf	sulfate
UC	ultracentrifugation
UPLC	ultra-performance liquid chromatography
Uro	uroolithin
WB	Western Blotting
ZP	zeta potential

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbio.2024.104888>.

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